

PURPOSE AND TASKS OF MODERN APPROACHES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: the article talks about the scientific theoretical importance of modern approaches and methods in teaching foreign languages. In particular, it was mentioned the advantages of integrative pedagogical activity and the importance of following certain principles when using this approach.

Key words: foreign language, educational system, integrative approach, inter-structural, text discourse, principle, method.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the process of globalization has covered all the countries of the world, and our country is no exception. At the same time as we are entering the world community with progressive steps, mastering foreign languages, including English, getting to know other peoples' customs, lifestyles and worldviews, and establishing diplomatic relations are gaining urgent importance. It should also be said that even people whose specialty is not related to learning foreign languages now realize that learning English will help them increase their professional opportunities. Today, it is becoming a requirement for foreign language specialists to be able to easily perform speech activities at an excellent level in other fields. In order to find a solution to the mentioned issues, the foundations of a relatively new memorization - integrative approach in the methodology of language teaching have been developed and are being used in the educational system of different countries. This article focuses on the content, purpose, tasks and types of this approach.

DISCUSSION

Integrative pedagogical activity is a unique pedagogical activity, which involves mixing different knowledge, laws or units used in another subject, or different departments in a subject, in learning a subject. 'swelling takes the process of bringing together. The meaning of the word "integration" refers to the process of combining separate parts into a single unit, making a whole out of parts. Y. A. Kamensky spoke about this for the first time in pedagogy, he said: "Knowledge that a person learns should not be separate and fragmented, but should be focused on interdependence and integrity", "Integration means not only connecting educational elements, but also finding solutions to problems that cannot be answered with the help of one discipline, with the help of the balance of other disciplines." Currently, integrated lessons are an important didactic tool for pedagogues, which, in turn, requires the creation of a system of integrated lessons or specially specialized programs and courses, in our case, English language teaching courses based on an integrative approach. Integrative sciences perform several tasks:

- Increases students' logical, erudite and critical thinking, their educational prospects;
- Develops general cultural, spiritual, speech and professional ability;

- *It helps students to acquire comprehensive knowledge instead of narrowly applied knowledge and skills.*

When using the integration method in education, it is permissible to focus on its structure and organizing components. These include: integration within and across disciplines; integration of horizontal and vertical theming; inter-structural and trans-disciplinary integration. An example of intra-disciplinary integration is the linking of grammatical units with textual discourse or phraseological units of lexicology, while cross-disciplinary integration is a text or main source in the teaching of English grammar through terminally enriched problem situations related to other disciplines or disciplines. Let's take as an example the collection of submitted assignments.

When using an integrative approach to teaching Shet languages, the following principles should be followed:

- ❖ *The principle of cultural compatibility;*
- ❖ *The principle of creativity;*
- ❖ *The principle of personal development and independent education;*
- ❖ *The principle of variability;*
- ❖ *The principle of identifying and perfecting one's identity through intercultural relations;*
- ❖ *The principle of religious and racial tolerance;*
- ❖ *The principle of creating dialogues between cultures.*

If we emphasize the field of teaching English in higher education institutions, we can divide the application of the integrative approach into two branches: students with English as a major and students with no major related to the language. For learners of English as the main language, for example, for future linguists or teachers of foreign languages, we can take contexts that reflect other professional texts and problematic situations in an integrated manner in teaching English grammar. In this case, young personnel can easily study the language not only in educational institutions specializing in linguistics, but also in educational institutions specializing in medicine, technology or design.

At the same time, it is advisable to create programs based on an integrative approach in conducting ESP courses for other professions, that is, special professional specialized English classes. Having studied the literature on the topic, we divide the methods needed by pedagogues into the following three groups when using this approach in teaching English and other foreign languages:

- *a group of intellectual-research methods (research, cultural bias self-awareness, abstracts, projects method);*
- *group of communicative-problematic methods (problematic discussions on intercultural relations, role-playing method based on cultural relations, role-playing method that creates a professional and working environment);*
- *problem-seeking methods group of methods (using technical means, skates, web-quest, method of creating blogs).*

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth saying that foreign language programs conducted with the help of an integrative approach provide students with opportunities for self-awareness and self-development. Through this approach, the image of the world is fully formed in the minds of students, and their worldview and extralinguistic knowledge of the country where the

language is being studied also increases. In addition, it creates an opportunity for future language teachers to teach English without any restrictions in educational institutions focused on other activities. Of course, there is no doubt that the approach that creates such opportunities meets the needs of today's society.

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